

Studies in the Flavanone Series.

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In their investigation of the tinctorial properties of Jackwood, Perkin and Cope (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 715) found that Jackwood contains along with morin a second allied substance, called by them cyanomaclurin which is devoid of tinctorial property. When gently warmed with dilute alkali, it gives a beautiful indigo colouration. It has the formula $C_{15}H_{12}O_6$ and on fusion with alkali gives β -resorcylic acid and phloroglucinol. Perkin suggested that cyanomaclurin is possibly the reduction product of morin just as catechin is that of quercetin and assigned to it among others the following constitution :

But the above constitution has not been established definitely (*vide* Bhalla and Rây, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 288). It appeared to us worth while to consider the possibility of a flavanone structure for cyanomaclurin in view of the fact that flavanones have been found within recent times to occur largely among natural products.

It agrees well with the molecular formula and decomposition products. The characteristic colouration of flavanones with magnesium

powder and alcoholic hydrochloric acid, as was given by cyanomaclurin isolated in our laboratory, lent additional support to the above view. We, therefore, took up the synthesis of cyanomaclurin or at least the synthesis of a substance of the above constitution, which, even if it would fail to give synthetic cyanomaclurin itself, would settle after all one side of the question.

Our first attempt was to prepare the flavanone according to the method of Shinoda and others (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1928, II, 1885; 1930, I, 229) by condensing phloroglucinol in nitrobenzene solution in presence of aluminium chloride with 2:4-dihydroxycinnamoyl chloride with the OH groups suitably protected. 2:4-Dimethoxy-cinnamic acid was prepared at first but all attempts for its demethylation failed.

It has been found that resorcylic- β -aldehyde does not condense with malonic acid and attempts to prepare the dicarbomethoxycinnamic acid by condensing the dicarbomethoxy- β -resorcylicaldehyde with malonic acid in pyridine solution in presence of piperidine also failed. Pyridine, in all probability, decarbomethoxylated the aldehyde and the hydroxy aldehyde thus produced could not condense with malonic acid.

The condensation was next attempted in glacial acetic acid solution (Spath, *Monatsch*, 1920, 41, 271). Dicarbomethoxy- β -resorcylicaldehyde was condensed with malonic acid in glacial acetic acid solution on a boiling water-bath for a varying number of hours (16, 8, 4, 2, 1). But in all cases the product instead of being 2:4-dicarbomethoxybenzalmalonic acid was found to be a mixture of two substances, 2:4-dicarbomethoxycinnamic acid (a trace) and carbomethoxyumbelliferone carboxylic acid. When boiled with sodium bicarbonate solution the latter gives umbelliferonecarboxylic acid, m.p. 262°, the carbomethoxy group being knocked off and the latter on heating gives umbelliferone, m.p. 225°.

Having no other alternative it was decided to proceed with 2:4-dimethoxycinnamic acid which could be easily obtained in quantity. Attempts were also made to convert the above acid into the corresponding acid chloride but also to no purpose. PCl_3 was next added to the solution of the acid in benzene and allowed to react at a low temperature. On treatment with alcohol, the solution gave the ester of known melting point. All attempts to isolate the chloride, however, met with failure. It was too sensitive and decomposed on slight exposure to air. Further reaction was attempted

in situ. Nitrobenzene was added to the benzene solution of the acid chloride, benzene was distilled off under reduced pressure and to the nitrobenzene solution of the acid chloride phloroglucinol, dissolved in dry ether, was added in presence of AlCl_3 . The condensation product, which was expected to contain the flavanone in question, was separated from nitrobenzene by steam distillation. It was dissolved in alkali and carbon dioxide was passed in. A very minute quantity of white slime was obtained which gave pink colouration with magnesium powder and alcoholic hydrochloric acid the well known test for flavanones. The flavanone, thus obtained, could not, however, by any means be collected in appreciable quantity and could not, therefore, be identified.

The acid chloride was next prepared in nitrobenzene solution directly and condensation was attempted but all in vain.

Attention was then directed to the synthesis of a product obtained by the fission of the ring of cyanomaclurin isolated from Jackwood in our laboratory and methylating the same.

It was thought that if the assumption of cyanomaclurin having a flavanone structure be correct, the synthesis of the chalkone would produce valuable evidence in its support. Trimethylphloracetophenone, prepared from phloroglucinol trimethyl ether and acetyl chloride (Kostanecki and Tambor, *Ber.*, 1899, 32, 2261) was condensed with dimethyl- β -resorcylaldehyde in presence of 10% NaOH giving 2:4:6:2':4'-pentamethoxychalkone, m.p. 124° .

The chalkone, however, was not found identical with the substance isolated from Jackwood which had melting point near about 240° . It was supposed that the difference between the two might be due to geometrical isomerism as both the substances contain double bonds and that if the natural compound as well as the synthetic one be reduced, the two might become identical.

The synthetic chalkone, on reduction with hydrogen in presence of platinum oxide as catalyst, gave a saturated ketone, 2:4:6:2':4'-pentamethoxydihydrochalkone.

The reduced ketone also combined with piperonal in presence of 10% caustic soda giving 2:4:6-trimethoxybenzoyl-2':4'-dimethoxy-

benzyl-3':4'-methylenedioxybenzylidenemethane.

Attempts are now being made in this laboratory to collect the supposed natural pentamethoxychalkone in appreciable quantity which will be reduced and compared with the synthetic one.

The ease and readiness with which the chalkone was synthesised tempted us naturally to follow the classical method of Kostanecki's morin synthesis (*Ber.*, 1906, **39**, 625), so that having obtained some amount of 4:6:2':4'-tetramethoxyflavanone by the method the expected cyanomaclurin would be obtained by one simple step of demethylation.

Dimethylphloracetophenone (*Ber.*, 1899, **32**, 2262) was condensed with dimethyl β -resorcyaldehyde giving 2-oxy-4:6:2':4'-tetramethoxychalkone which melted sharply at 125° and not at 152° as recorded by Kostanecki.

Attempts were made to prepare the flavanone by ring closure according to Freudenberg's modification of Kostanecki's flavanone synthesis (*Ber.*, 1922, 55, 1748). A small amount of crude flavanone was obtained melting between 160-68° (Kostanecki, 168°). But when attempt was made to recrystallise the substance, almost no flavanone was left behind.

The chalkone was reduced by means of hydrogen with platinum oxide as catalyst and gave 2-oxy-4:6:2':4'-tetramethoxydihydrochalkone, m. p. 100°, which on methylation with methyl sulphate

and alkali gave a completely methylated ketone, m. p. 80°, which was found identical with the pentamethoxydihydrochalkone already prepared.

EXPERIMENTAL.

2:4-Dimethoxycinnamic acid.—2:4-Dimethoxy- β -resorcyraldehyde (8 g.) and malonic acid (12 g.) were dissolved in pyridine (24 c. c.) and a few drops of piperidine were then added and the mixture refluxed for an hour on a boiling water-bath. when CO_2 was evolved. The mixture was then heated for 5 minutes on a sand bath to complete the reaction, allowed to cool under the tap and acidified with hydrochloric acid (1:1), when there was copious white precipitate of the dimethoxycinnamic acid. It was collected, washed, dried and crystallised from acetic acid in white scales, m. p. 187°, yield 10 g. (Found: C, 63.38; H, 5.84; OCH_3 , 30%; M. W. 210. $\text{C}_9 \text{H}_6 \text{O}_2 (\text{OCH}_3)_2$ requires C, 63.46; H, 5.77; OCH_3 , 29.8 per cent. M. W. 208.)

Dicarbomethoxy- β -resorcyraldehyde.—A solution of β -resorcyraldehyde (6.9 g.) in acetone (30 c.c.) was treated with methyl chlorocarbonate (4.7 g.) and under ice cooling and constant shaking *N*-NaOH (50 c. c.) were gradually introduced. 40 C. c. more of acetone were added and the solution treated with methyl chlorocarbonate and *N*-NaOH twice more with continuous cooling and constant shaking, when dicarbomethoxy compound began to separate. On addition of an equal quantity of water, the substance was obtained in quantitative yield and recrystallised from dilute acetone, m. p. 72°. (Found: C, 51.7; H, 3.8. $\text{C}_{11} \text{H}_{10} \text{O}_7$ requires C, 51.9; H, 3.9 per cent.)

The *phenylhydrazone* crystallised from dilute alcohol in sandy crystals, m. p. 138°. (Found: N, 7.8. $C_{17}H_{16}O_6N_2$ requires N, 8.1 per cent).

The *semicarbazone*, prepared in the usual manner, crystallised from acetic acid in white sandy crystals, m. p. 185°. (Found: N, 13.2. $C_{12}H_{13}O_7N_3$ requires N, 13.5 per cent).

Dicarbomethoxy- β -resorcylic acid.—Potassium permanganate (2 g. in 33.2 c.c. of water) was added to a solution of dicarbomethoxy- β -resorcyraldehyde (2 g.) in acetone (16.6 c. c.) with constant shaking in the course of 30 to 45 minutes, the temperature being kept between 40-45° all throughout. The manganese dioxide was removed with SO_2 leaving a white precipitate of dicarbomethoxy- β -resorcylic acid, which was recrystallised from dilute acetone, m. p. 159°. (Found: C, 48.7; H, 3.7. $C_{11}H_{10}O_8$ requires C, 48.8; H, 3.7 per cent).

2:4-Dicarbomethoxycinnamic acid and carbomethoxyumbelliferone carboxylic acid.—Dicarbomethoxy- β -resorcyraldehyde (8 g.) and malonic acid (13 g.) were dissolved in glacial acetic acid (13 g.) and heated on a boiling water-bath (16 hours). On cooling the solution was diluted with water and the precipitate consisting of dicarbomethoxycinnamic acid and carbomethoxyumbelliferone carboxylic acid treated with 10% potassium bicarbonate solution under ice cooling. The cinnamic acid passed into solution, while the other remained insoluble. The filtrate was acidified with hydrochloric acid and recrystallised from dilute alcohol as beautiful white silky needles, m. p. 190°. (Found: C, 52.95; H, 3.82. $C_{13}H_{12}O_8$ requires C, 52.7; H, 4.07 per cent). The residue was crystallised from acetic acid as beautiful white needles, m. p. 201-02°. (Found: C, 54.84; H, 3.11. $C_{12}H_8O_7$ requires C, 54.54; H, 3.03 per cent).

Carbomethoxyumbelliferone carboxylic acid (2 g.) was boiled with an excess of 10% sodium carbonate solution for 15 minutes. A highly blue fluorescent solution was obtained which on acidification with hydrochloric acid (1:1) gave a white precipitate of umbelliferone carboxylic acid, which crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 262° and when heated 4—5° above its m. p. for 15 minutes gave umbelliferone, m.p. 225°. (Found: C, 58.0; H, 2.9. Calc: C, 58.2; H, 2.9 per cent).

2:4:6:2':4'-Pentamethoxychalkone.—Caustic soda (5%, 10 g.) solution was added to a solution of phloracetophenone trimethyl ether (5 g.) and dimethyl- β -resorcyraldehyde (4 g.) in alcohol (50 c.c.). After standing for a time in a warm place, the whole solidified to a yellow mass. This was poured into dilute hydrochloric acid and the

precipitate was collected and pressed on a porous plate and crystallised from alcohol in pale yellow crystals, m.p. 124° , yield 5 g. (Found: C, 66.8; H, 6.0. $C_{20}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 67.04; H, 6.14 per cent).

2:4:6:2':4'-Pentamethoxydihydrochalkone.— A solution of the pentamethoxychalkone (5 g.) in pure ethyl acetate (100 c.c.) was taken in a hydrogenation flask with platinum oxide (0.1 g.) added as catalyst. The flask was evacuated and connected with the hydrogen cylinder and shaken, when absorption of hydrogen took place. In about 3 hours theoretical amount of hydrogen was absorbed when the flask was disconnected and the solution filtered from the platinum oxide through a Gooch. Ethyl acetate was distilled off on the water-bath and a thick oil was obtained which solidified to a mass of colourless crystals after a time. It crystallised from dilute alcohol in well-defined colourless rhombic plates, m.p. 80° , yield theoretical. (Found: C, 66.06; H, 5.9. $C_{20}H_{24}O_6$ requires C, 66.6; H, 6.6 per cent).

The *oxime*, prepared in the usual manner, crystallised from dilute alcohol as shining colourless crystals, m. p. 142° . (Found: N, 3.4. $C_{20}H_{25}O_6N$ requires N, 3.7 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 134° . (Found: N, 13.0. $C_{21}H_{27}O_6N_3$ requires N, 13.1 per cent).

2:4:6-Trimethoxybenzoyl-2':4'-dimethoxybenzyl-3'' : 4''-methylene-dioxybenzylidene methane.—2:4:6-Trimethoxybenzoyl-2:4-dimethoxybenzylmethane (1 g.) and piperonal (0.4 g.) were dissolved in alcohol (10 c.c.) and to the warm solution NaOH solution (50%, 2 g.) was added. After standing for a time in a warm place, the whole solidified to a pale yellow mass. This was then poured into dilute hydrochloric acid and filtered. The product crystallised from acetic acid in shining crystals, m. p. 215° , yield 1 g. (Found: C, 68.0; H, 5.4. $C_{28}H_{28}O_8$ requires C, 68.29; H, 5.69 per cent).

2-Oxy-4:6:2':4'-tetramethoxychalkone.—To the warm solution of phloracetophenone dimethyl ether (2 g.) and dimethyl- β resorcyaldehyde (1.6 g.) in alcohol (20 c.c.) NaOH solution (50%, 4 g.) was added. After standing for a short time the whole solidified to an intense yellow mass. This was then just neutralised with dilute hydrochloric acid and the precipitate collected, pressed on a porous plate and crystallised from alcohol in yellow crystals, m.p. 125° , the melting point does not change in the least even after repeated crystallisations for six times (Kostaneccki, m. p. 152°). (Found: C,

66.43; H, 5.84; OMe, 36.0. $C_{19}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 66.3; H, 5.80; OMe, 36.5 per cent).

2-Oxy-4:6:2':4'-Tetramethoxydihydrochalkone. — The hydroxy-tetramethoxychalkone (2 g.) was dissolved in pure ethyl acetate (30 c.c.) and was then reduced by means of hydrogen with platinum oxide (0.05 g.) as catalyst exactly in the same manner as in the reduction of 2:4:6:2':4'-pentamethoxychalkone. On distilling off the ethyl acetate a thick oil was obtained which readily solidified on rubbing with a little ether to canary yellow crystals. It crystallised from ether, m. p. 100°. On methylation with methyl sulphate and alkali it gave 2:4:6:2':4'-pentamethoxydihydrochalkone which proves to be identical with the pentamethoxy saturated ketone synthesised before. (Found: C, 65.5; H, 5.90. $C_{19}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 65.8; H, 6.30 per cent).

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